

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14558481>

INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES

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Annotation: *in this article, the school program structure on the subject “natural”, to give students an idea of the problems of the present time, to find solutions to problems related to natural science, to improve environmental thinking, to analyze the facts of students, to create a mechanism of links in the study of phenomena and processes, to master the educational material through the application, Natural Sciences educational content the continuity of knowledge regarding various academic disciplines studying the problems surrounding human and Nature Communication has been described using modern educational technologies.*

Key words: *Innovation, Experience, Design, real world, student-oriented education, real world context, criticism, thinking, problem, collaboration and communication, integration of technology.*

ИННОВАЦИОННЫЙ ПОДХОД К МЕТОДИКЕ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫХ НАУК

Аннотация: *В данной статье проектное обучение может стать одним из инновационных подходов к преподаванию естественных наук. Эта методология побуждает студентов активно участвовать в практических проектах или экспериментах для изучения научных концепций.*

Ключевые слова: *инновации, опыт, дизайн, реальный мир, личностно-ориентированное обучение, контекст реального мира, критика, мышление, решение проблем, сотрудничество и общение, интеграция технологий.*

Positive changes in the development of the school education system in our country have their impact and Uzbekistan has entered the world arena. There is an opportunity to compare the achieved results with others, to master positive aspects from others. In the implementation of a new system of education in our republic, the need for education reform of our Prezident has become an urgent task. To this end, the use of innovation technologies in the teaching of Natural Sciences in secondary schools is of urgent importance.

The study of the connections between objects and phenomena in the teaching of Natural Sciences is necessary for the formation and development of basic concepts in the field of “surrounding nature”. This work stimulates the mental activity of children. Activates the learning process. As a result of the fact that children learn certain contacts in the course of the lesson, the question arises in them as follows: Why do these contacts exist? In the study of natural and anthropogenic regions (spatial and temporal) communications are used on the basis of a comparative method.

Initially, connections are made between the two indicators, and the attention of schoolchildren is focused precisely on the compared elements. The next step in forming the idea of the interconnection of objects and phenomena of nature is the installation by children of link chains such as “tree leaf - insect – bird”, “the height of the sun from the Horizon - Air, soil, reservoir temperature - insect extinction - flying migratory birds”.

The final stage in the study of the interaction of objects and phenomena of nature is the determination of their causes, mechanism. This happens, as a rule, at the level of concept formation. In the course of the lesson, the formation of the need for independent knowledge in the student, the size of the volume of materials to be studied, the variability of the processes to be considered, the introduction of the latest methods in teaching the modern elementary class natural science is a requirement of the present day. The main essence of innovative pedagogical Technologies is to train students in education with interest and achieve complete mastery of their knowledge. For this, it is considered extremely important for the teacher to correctly select teaching methods in natural science lessons in accordance with the topic. If the appropriate method is incorrectly selected, the joint activities of the teacher and the student will remain ineffective. Therefore, when choosing teaching methods, methods should be carried out based on their tasks.

Another of the innovative technology models is project activities. In the process of teaching natural sciences, there is a wide range of opportunities for the application of project activities. 1. Mini projects in the classroom. This type of work is often used. When studying various subjects in grades 3-4, they create various project work, projects for the development of mineral deposits. Such tasks are given to children for

the entire period of study of the branches of Natural Science. At the end of the study of the topic, students must present a draft of any object of nature and natural processes and make a survey of their developments based on the knowledge gained in the process of studying this topic.

2. Projects can be long-term. For example, year-round students in Year 4 present a hypothetical continental model. They draw on it all sorts of thematic maps, invent new countries and cities for it, make a history of discovery and research. Work on such a project is carried out during the academic year. In the first stage, students are determined by the location of the future continent on the map. Its geographical position is determined, it is determined which oceans washed this continent, adjacent to other continents. Thus, the new continent will receive "registration" on the world map.

In addition, in the process of studying each new topic, different geographical objects appear on the continent. Students work on projects individually and in groups. Groups are selected taking into account the ability and motivation of students. Each should have both strong and weak students in the group. The work is distributed in such a way that each child participates in the project. Tasks are selected taking into account the abilities and level of development of each child.

Project "Green Pharmacy" In addition to the project activities, there are great opportunities in terms of the formation of the ecological culture of schoolchildren of younger age. An example of a cognitive research project is the development of a "plant pharmacy". By the composition of the participants, this is a team project (1st graders and their parents), by duration-medium-term.

- * study of medicinal properties of plants;
- * nurture respect for nature;
- * development of creative and cognitive activity;
- * formation of research qualifications.

During the work, the teacher asks the children the question: Can plants replace medicines? To answer this, use the following types of work:

- organization Book Fair, creating ecological costumes from medicinal herbs, watching educational films;
- * conversations, Tips, Quizzes;
- asking problematic questions, observations, experiments, research, further information; Visiting a pharmacy, a role-playing game, organizing an ecological holiday, creating a booklet about medicinal herbs

Innovative activities provide an opportunity for the teacher: Professional growth; emotional satisfaction; the possibility of self-development; organization of differentiated education; prediction of educational results; early diagnosis and correction of educational results. The student is given a choice: Level, volume, content

of subject knowledge(not lower than the standard); source of information for mastering the selected volume of knowledge; method of training according to individual personal characteristics (type of thinking, memory characteristics); pace of development on the subject corresponding to personal characteristics; form, type and time of control and self-control; partner for communication; role of a listener or.

The process develops skills: Independent activity; communicative activity. The diagnosis of the results obtained is carried out in the following form: observations; conversations; questionnaires; exchange of experience in teachers ' councils, seminars; calculation of the independence coefficient; summarizing the results of the trimester, half-year; passing exams in a new format.

Thanks to the use of Game Technology, schoolchildren acquire decision-making skills based on activation of their activities, search for ways to solve the problem, reflection. The game is an important incentive in learning. During the game, the child has the opportunity to realize his potential opportunities, get high marks. At the same time, during the game, schoolchildren activate the ability to focus, imagination, memory, analyze, compare and draw conclusions. The game allows me to involve each child in active work, in which there is an interest in reincarnation and improvisation, special conditions are created for students to independently seek knowledge.

Role-playing games in the education and upbringing of children occupy a special place in classes. It is a special form of joint life between children and adults, in which children model Adult Activities, its meaning, tasks, norms of relationships. Such a game has a certain effect on the formation of the child's personality. The activity component plays an important role in the biological and environmental education of the school. It is in nature that biological and environmental knowledge is formed in the process of performing certain actions, predicting the consequences of their actions in the environment, practical activity.

Therefore, in organized classes of teaching based on innovative technologies, the student develops theoretical and practical training on the basis of an innovative approach, as well as his independent research, analysis and crop thinking, decision-making abilities creative thinking as elements of competence. Also, the opportunities for the teacher to choose methods and forms of Education will expand.

Training assignments developed on the basis of Universal education provide a more accurate result in the control and assessment of knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies acquired by students, and the teacher an opportunity to accurately and realistically, fairly assess the acquired knowledge of students.

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